

THE MAIN TYPES OF LEARNING STYLES IN THE CLASSROOM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10868016>

Abstract: This article describes learning styles in the classroom and refers to three basic types of learning styles: visual, auditory, and kinesthetic. Learning styles also take into account various methods of understanding and retaining information.

Keywords: learning, style, visual-auditory, kinesthetic, methods, and improved skills.

Learning style has to do with how people bring new information into their knowledge base. Knowing your learning style enables you to use your strengths as you study for courses. While there are many models and theories about learning styles, one popular framework is the VARK model, developed by Neil Fleming in 1987¹. According to the VARK model, there are four primary learning styles: People have diverse learning preferences. While some excel with written materials, others thrive with auditory learning. Certain individuals prefer quiet environments like libraries or home offices, whereas others learn best when they're physically active or involved in hands-on tasks. There are three basic types of classroom learning styles: visual, auditory, and kinesthetic. These learning styles describe the most common over the others; thus, each person has a learning style that is dominant even though he or she may also rely somewhat on the other approaches at different times and in different circumstances. The first style is visual learning. Visual learners prefer to sit somewhere in the classroom where no obstructions hinder their view of the lesson. They rely on the teacher's facial expressions and body language for their learning. They learn best from a blend of visual displays and presentations such as colorful² videos, diagrams, and flip charts. They have a lack of confidence in their auditory memory skills and so may take detailed notes during classroom discussions or lessons. The next style is auditory learning: Auditory learners learn best through listening and speaking. They benefit from lectures, discussions, and audio recordings. Techniques that can help auditory learners include reading information aloud, explaining concepts to others, and using mnemonic devices that involve rhythm or rhyme. Furthermore, where they sit, they can hear very well and they enjoy listening, so discussions and verbal lectures stimulate them. The type of learners can get information easily by reading somebody who reads loudly. Sounding spelling words, reciting mathematical theories, or talking their way across a map are examples of the types of activities that improve their understanding. Another type of learning is kinesthetic learning: Kinesthetic learners learn best through hands-on experiences and physical activities. They benefit from doing experiments, using manipulatives, and engaging in role-playing exercises. These types of learners have difficulty sitting in a classroom. Sometimes they need to be physically active and have some breaks during lessons or discussions. When they start bored, they often fidget in a conventional classroom setting. They are good at learning mathematics, science, and drawing activities. Also, they have a good ability to process new information. Many scientists have

¹ <https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/achieving-success-in-second-language-acquisition/learning-styles-and-learning-strategies/6DE55B4DF17A3230D13A60F7B81E0A47>

² BrE: colourful

researched learning styles. Richard E. Mayer,³ a professor of psychology at the University of California, Santa Barbara, is known for his research on learning and instructional design. Mayer's work often emphasizes the importance of evidence-based instructional strategies. While he acknowledges that individuals may have preferences for how they learn, he suggests that these preferences may not necessarily correlate with improved learning outcomes. Mayer advocates for instructional approaches that are grounded in cognitive science research. In upper levels of education, it's beneficial to understand their learning style and adapt their study techniques accordingly. This can help them get knowledge well and retain information more effectively. Thus, mixing different learning styles can enhance their overall understanding of the material.

Moreover, learning style is main best way to learn a new language or determine how students learn a new language. According to Hilliard (2001), learning styles are the characteristic ways in which an individual acquires, perceives, and processes information.⁴ It's important to note that while many people have a dominant learning style, individuals often have a combination of preferences and may learn effectively through multiple modalities. Additionally, research on the effectiveness of teaching strategies tailored to specific learning styles has been mixed, with some studies suggesting that matching instruction to learning styles may not significantly improve learning outcomes. Understanding one's own learning style can be beneficial in developing effective study strategies, but it's also important for educators to recognize and accommodate diverse learning preferences within their teaching practices. Flexibility in teaching methods and providing opportunities for students to engage with material in different ways can help support a variety of learning styles in the classroom.

Other learning style models include the Honey and Mumford model, which categorizes learners into four styles: activist, reflector, theorist, and pragmatist, based on their approach to learning tasks. There's also Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory, which proposes four stages of learning: concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation.⁵ Traditional methods of learning involve students sitting at desks, listening to teachers, and working in textbooks. However, educators have evolved their approaches, and modern classrooms no longer adhere strictly to these practices. Instead, teachers incorporate activities into their lessons that cater to the diverse learning needs of all students.

To sum up, researches show that most students use these types of learning styles in utilizing different parts of their brains. we know that teachers should use a range of styles while presenting their lessons and it is a really good idea for teachers to expose students to a kind of learning experience.

References:

1. Florida University, learning types, and strategies:

³ Taken from encyclopedia barrons for IELTS

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https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351665507_Auditory_and_kinaesthetic_learning_styles_and_L2_achievement_A_correlational_study

⁵ <https://eltguide.com/learning-strategies-learning-styles/>

2. The VARK system categorizes learners into four styles: Visual, Aural, Reading/Writing, and Kinesthetic. Many learners show strength in more than one learning ...
3. Books encyclopedia Auditory learning Lougheed, Lin, (1949).
4. Wilfried Laurier University (2008) Understanding your learning styles.

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